

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE SPLEEN IN EXPERIMENTAL RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS WITH THE HELP OF ADJUVANT FREYEND

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Research relevance: the immune system is one of the most complex autonomous regulatory systems of the body, therefore, violation of its functionality leads to serious complications of an autoimmune and infectious nature. "In this regard, in recent years, the issues of maintaining homeostasis in the immune system have become especially relevant." The protection of a living organism cannot be imagined without an immune system. In humans and animals, the immune system provides the body's flexibility and protection against the effects of various pathogenic factors. In recent years, there has been an increase in diseases associated with damage to the immune system in the world". Currently, the degree of the body's immune reactivity undoubtedly determines the course and consequences of most diseases. The state of health of modern society is characterized by a decrease in immune reactivity, as a result, an increase in acute and chronic diseases." In the world, a number of scientific studies are being carried out aimed at assessing the changes in morphological and morphometric indicators of the spleen under the influence of rheumatoid arthritis disease and auxiliary Freund induced arthritis. In this regard, it is required to substantiate age-related normative, rheumatoid arthritis and morphological and morphometric indicators of the spleen of white-breed rats in postnatal ontogenesis, to compare morphometric indicators of spleen lymphoid structures in rheumatoid arthritis with indicators of healthy laboratory animals, to study morphological and morphometric changes that occur in their spleen when administering rheumatoid in arthritis.

The purpose of the study. Study of morphological, morphometric and immunogistochemical indicators of the White Rat spleen in the treatment of experimental rheumatoid arthritis and postpatogenetics.

Materials and methods: for the modeling of rheumatoid arthritis, a full-fledged Freund assistant was used in 100 white randomized rats aged 18 to 24 months under the stationary conditions of the vivarium of the Bukhara State Medical Institute.

Results: age-related morphological and morphometric changes are justified in postnatal ontogenesis in the White Rat spleen after rheumatoid arthritis and under the influence of the adjuvant Freyend. The study of structural changes in postnatal ontogenesis of the White Rat spleen in rheumatoid arthritis disease and under the influence of Freyend's blanket is based on the possibility of determining the most dangerous age periods;

The data obtained in the study is based on the fact that it is important to identify the development of immunopathological processes that occur under the influence of rheumatoid arthritis in the early stages, to prevent it and to develop effective treatments.

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